

GAN-based bone suppression using a combined loss function

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Accurate analysis of chest X-rays is essential for the diagnosis of diseases such as pneumonia
4 and lung cancer. However, bone structures obscure critical soft tissues and lesions, hindering
5 visualization. This study proposes advanced machine learning methods for bone suppression
6 to improve image clarity and assist radiologists in making accurate diagnoses. We developed
7 and compared deep learning architectures, including Autoencoders, U-Nets, and Generative
8 Adversarial Networks (GANs), focusing on Wasserstein GANs and Spatial Feature and Resolution
9 Maximization GAN. Key innovations include an enhanced GAN architecture with improved
10 generator and discriminator components for feature extraction and high-resolution outputs. Our
11 model integrates a U-Net-based generator, enabling precise localization of critical features while
12 preserving soft tissues. Regularization techniques and a combined loss function (Wasserstein
13 Loss, L_1 , Perceptual Loss, Sobel Loss) were implemented to improve generalization and stability.
14 Among the proposed methods, the GAN-based model demonstrated the best performance in
15 internal comparisons, achieving a Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) of 44.09 dB and a Multi-
16 Scale Structural Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM) of 0.9968. Furthermore, this model was
17 compared with other recently published methods, achieving the best result with an MS-SSIM of
18 0.997 and a PSNR of 44.09. The proposed GAN offers a robust solution for bone suppression
19 in chest X-rays, significantly improving the visibility of the lung region. This approach has the
20 potential to improve the detection of small lesions and nodules, making it a valuable tool for
21 medical imaging preprocessing and clinical workflows.

22 **Keywords:** Generative Adversarial Network, Autoencoders, U-net, Bone Suppression, Chest Radiographs, X-ray Image Analysis,
23 Computer-Aided Diagnosis, Combined Loss Function

1 INTRODUCTION

24 X-rays play an important role in medical diagnostics, helping healthcare professionals identify various
25 conditions and guide treatment plans. However, traditional X-ray images often present challenges due
26 to the presence of bone structures, which can hinder accurate diagnosis by casting shadows over parts
27 of the lesion, leading to potential misinterpretations. Furthermore, ionizing radiation poses a significant
28 risk to the human body, especially with repeated exposure; therefore, the current trend is to minimize this
29 radiation as much as possible (Hong et al., 2021). However, reducing radiation doses decreases the quality
30 of the resulting images, making diagnosis even more difficult (Uffmann and Schaefer-Prokop, 2009). For

31 this reason, computational image processing techniques for the suppression of bones (ribs) from chest
32 radiographs have become a part of assisted radiology (Schalekamp et al., 2013; Bae et al., 2022) and are an
33 important preprocessing step in computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) (Horváth et al., 2013; Elgohary et al.,
34 2022), contributing to the correct classification of lung disease (Han et al., 2022). This is mainly due to
35 the use of convolutional neural networks, which have been a phenomenon in recent years because they
36 can offer high accuracy and robust performance. We proposed a GAN-based method (Arjovsky et al.,
37 2017; Rani et al., 2022) to generate chest images with bones removed and compared it with other neural
38 network-based methods widely used in image processing, namely autoencoders (Bank et al., 2020; Vincent
39 et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2018) and U-net (Zhou et al., 2020; Gusarev et al., 2017). To illustrate the potential
40 impact of our method, we provide the following example: Figure 1 presents an original X-ray image of
41 the lungs, where bone structures obscure the visibility of lung tissues. The application of our software, as
42 demonstrated in the processed images, effectively removes these bone structures, thereby enhancing the
43 clarity of soft tissue details. This improved visualization supports healthcare professionals in making more
44 precise assessments, potentially leading to more accurate diagnoses and optimized treatment strategies,
45 ultimately contributing to improved patient care.

Figure 1. Image a is original image from the X-ray, image b is output image with removed bones.

46 We conducted extensive experiments to evaluate the performance of our bone removal software using
47 various architectures and loss functions. The best results were achieved with the GAN neural network, with
48 a Multiscale Structural Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM) of **0.9968** and a Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
49 (PSNR) of **44.09 db**.

50 **Bones Removal Dataset**

51 In 1998, the Academic Committee of the Japanese Society of Radiological Technology (JSRT) launched
52 an initiative to establish the Standard Digital Image Database, a collection of chest radiographs containing
53 both normal cases and cases with lung nodules. This effort, undertaken in collaboration with the Japan
54 Radiological Society, was made possible through contributions of clinical cases from medical institutions in
55 both Japan and the United States. Over the years, the JSRT database has become a widely utilized resource
56 in medical imaging research, facilitating advancements in image processing, compression techniques,

57 display assessments, Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS), and the development of
58 machine learning-based computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems. The database comprises 247 digitized
59 chest radiographs (CXR), including 154 cases with lung nodules – 100 classified as malignant, 54 as
60 benign, and 93 cases without nodules. These images were digitized using a laser scanner at a resolution of
61 2048×2048 pixels (0.175 mm per pixel) with a 12-bit grayscale depth. The images are stored in big-endian
62 raw format without headers (Shiraishi et al., 2000). To expand the dataset, various augmentation techniques
63 were employed, including affine transformations such as rotation (-10 to 10 degrees), horizontal and vertical
64 translation (-5 to 5 pixels), horizontal flipping, and zooming. Additionally, image processing techniques
65 such as median filtering, maximum and minimum filtering, and unsharp masking were applied. As a result,
66 the dataset was expanded to 4081 image pairs at a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels, consisting of both the
67 original CXRs and their corresponding bone-suppressed versions (Rajaraman et al., 2021). An example of
68 these images is provided in Figure 2, where the upper image displays a chest radiograph containing lung
69 nodules, and the lower image presents the same radiograph with suppressed bone structures.

Figure 2. Example of images from augmented JSRT dataset

2 METHODS

70 In this section, we present three deep learning strategies for bone suppression, each of which has been
71 custom-implemented to align with the architectures proposed in their foundational works. First, we designed
72 a custom Autoencoder architecture inspired by the original model (Gondara, 2016), modifying certain
73 layers and hyperparameters to better suit our objective of bone suppression. Second, we developed a U-Net
74 (Ronneberger et al., 2015) that closely follows the encoder-decoder structure described by Ronneberger
75 et al. but includes adjustments for improved handling of subtle bone features. Lastly, we constructed a
76 custom GAN model by combining key ideas from both the SFRM-GAN (Rani et al., 2022) and Wasserstein
77 GAN (Arjovsky et al., 2017) frameworks, ensuring that it could learn to suppress bones robustly without
78 sacrificing overall image fidelity.

79 2.1 Autoencoder

80 An autoencoder is a specific type of neural network that is primarily designed to encode input data
81 into a compressed representation and then reconstruct it to resemble the original as closely as possible.
82 Autoencoders are widely used in applications such as dimensionality reduction (Meng et al., 2017; Wang
83 et al., 2014), classification (Luo et al., 2017), anomaly detection (Sakurada and Yairi, 2014), and noise
84 reduction (Chiang et al., 2019; Bengio et al., 2013; Creswell and Bharath, 2019). For noise reduction,
85 denoising autoencoders are frequently employed. In these models, a noise layer is introduced immediately
86 after the input layer, followed by training the hidden and reconstruction layers with data that include noise.
87 A denoising autoencoder is an extension of a conventional autoencoder, in which the model learns to
88 map corrupted data to uncorrupted data by minimizing the loss function between their representations
89 (Bank et al., 2020). The learning objective of this model is to recover the clean input from the noisy and
90 corrupted version. The corrupted signal, \tilde{X} , is generated from the clean signal, X , by random mapping
91 $\tilde{X} \sim q_D(\tilde{X}|X)$ (Li et al., 2023).

92 In this work, a convolutional denoising autoencoder (CDAE) (Gondara, 2016) was used to address the
93 challenge posed by the ribs, which act as unwanted noise in chest X-ray images (CXR). Unlike traditional
94 fully connected layers, the convolutional autoencoder employs convolution and pooling operations within
95 the convolutional neural network, effectively preserving two-dimensional spatial information (Li et al.,
96 2023). It is well suited for images, as it preserves spatial locality by sharing weights across all input
97 locations. Gondara et al. have shown (Gondara, 2016) that CDA can be used for efficient denoising of
98 medical images by using small training datasets to achieve good performance. The ability of CDAEs to
99 effectively denoise medical images using a model trained on a relatively small training dataset has also been
100 demonstrated by (Lee et al., 2018) on chest radiograph images. Kalish et al. (Kalisz and Marczyk, 2021)
101 developed a CDAE-based architecture and trained a model on the Bone Suppression dataset to remove
102 bones from chest radiographs (COVIDx dataset). Ahmed et al. (Ahmed et al., 2021) employed a stacked
103 convolutional autoencoder (SCAE), an improved form of a basic denoising autoencoder with integrated
104 convolutional layers, to reduce noise in two-dimensional gel electrophoresis (2-DGE) images.

105 The input to the autoencoder consists of a $1024 \times 1024 \times 1$ image normalized to the range $[0, 1]$.

106 The convolutional autoencoder architecture in Figure 3 used for bone suppression operates on an encoder-
107 decoder framework. The encoder, composed of convolutional and cluster layers, extracts key features
108 while compressing the image into a compact representation, focusing on differentiating bones from other
109 structures. As the image moves through these layers, progressively abstract features are identified, from
110 basic edges to more complex structures like bone tissue.

111 The decoder then reconstructs the image in order to enhance the visibility of soft tissue while reducing
112 bone prominence. By focusing on features related to soft tissues, the autoencoder effectively separates
113 bone characteristics, producing a clearer image for diagnostic evaluation.

114 2.2 U-Net

115 U-net is an encoder-decoder model that is widely used in segmentation tasks, including the segmentation
116 of chest radiographs (Zheng et al., 2021; Osadebey et al., 2021; Novikov et al., 2018). Wang et al. (Wang
117 et al., 2020) proposed the multitask dense connection U-Net (MDU-Net) to address the challenge of
118 bone segmentation from a chest radiograph. Their method combines the U-Net multiscale feature fusion
119 approach, the DenseNet dense connection, and the multitasking mechanism to construct the proposed MDU-
120 Net. For bone removal, Cardenas et al. (Cardenas et al., 2021) used a U-Net architecture, demonstrating

Figure 3. Convolutional Autoencoder Architecture for Bone Suppression: The encoder-decoder framework begins with an encoder that uses convolutional (Conv2D) and pooling (MaxPooling2D) layers to extract and compress image features, focusing on distinguishing bones. Each layer progressively captures more abstract features. The decoder then reconstructs the image using upsampling layers (UpSampling2D), enhancing soft tissue visibility and reducing bone prominence. Here, f = number of filters and A = activation function either ReLU or Sigmoid.

121 that bone removal from chest radiographs is feasible using a CNN combined with a patch-based approach
 122 by effectively segmenting and excluding bone structures. To succeed in the bone suppression task, we
 123 must input X-ray images in which bone structures are prominent and must be distinguished from other
 124 tissues. The U-net architecture can be effective in this context, with its unique up-sampling and down-
 125 sampling layers. In this case, we are using an original model from the paper U-Net: Convolutional
 126 Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation (Ronneberger et al., 2015) together with various backbones
 127 of the Segmentation Model library (Iakubovskii, 2019). The input image to the U-net is $1024 \times 1024 \times 1$
 128 normalized in the range of $[0, 1]$. The proposed architectures can be seen in Figure 4.

129 At each layer of the encoder, the network applies filters to progressively extract image features, beginning
 130 with basic edge detection in the initial layers and advancing to more intricate patterns in the deeper layers.
 131 This hierarchical feature extraction is essential for distinguishing subtle differences between bones and
 132 surrounding tissues in radiographic images.

133 As the image passes through the encoder, its spatial resolution decreases while the extracted features
 134 become more abstract and informative. This trade-off allows the network to focus on the most relevant

Figure 4. The proposed U-Net architecture uses an encoder-decoder structure with skip connections. The encoder uses convolutional and pooling layers to capture progressively abstract image features, essential to distinguish bones from soft tissue. At the bottleneck, the image is compressed into a compact and detailed representation. The decoder then reconstructs the image with minimized bone features, using skip connections to retain fine-grained details. f = number of filters and A = activation function ReLU or Sigmoid.

135 characteristics, particularly those necessary for identifying and suppressing bone structures. Upon reaching
 136 the bottleneck layer—the transitional point between the encoder and decoder—the image is transformed
 137 into a compact yet information-rich representation, emphasizing the critical features required for effective
 138 bone suppression.

139 The decoder then reconstructs the image using this refined information, ensuring that bone features are
 140 minimized while preserving other anatomical structures. The encoder's precise extraction of bone-related
 141 features plays a crucial role in this process, enabling the decoder to accurately suppress bones in the final
 142 output. This systematic approach allows the network to accurately identify and modify bone structures
 143 while maintaining the visibility of other essential anatomical details. The synergy between the encoder and
 144 decoder in this process makes U-Net particularly effective for bone suppression in radiographic imaging,
 145 demonstrating a sophisticated approach that goes beyond conventional segmentation to achieve targeted
 146 image transformation.

147 2.3 Generative Adversarial Networks

148 Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) consist of two components: the generator (G) and the
 149 discriminator (D). Given a specific condition or input, the role of the generator is to produce realistic
 150 images that ideally should be indistinguishable from the target images (Creswell et al., 2018). Conversely,
 151 the discriminator is responsible for distinguishing between the generated images and the actual target

152 images. In the context of bone suppression, the generator is expected to learn how to generate images
 153 where bones are effectively suppressed.

154 Rani et al. (Rani et al., 2022) addressed the bone suppression task by modifying the architectures of
 155 both the generator and discriminator in the Pix2Pix model. Their approach improved performance and
 156 training stability by integrating the discriminator into the Wasserstein GAN framework, further enhanced
 157 with a Gradient Penalty. Similarly, Han et al. (Han et al., 2022) introduced a GAN-based disentanglement
 158 learning framework, termed Rib Suppression GAN (RSGAN), to perform rib suppression by leveraging
 159 anatomical knowledge embedded in unpaired CT images. Their method focuses on predicting the residual
 160 map between the input chest X-ray (CXR) and its corresponding rib-suppressed version.

161 Our proposed architecture is inspired by the Wasserstein GAN (Arjovsky et al., 2017) and the Spatial
 162 Feature and Resolution Maximization GAN (SFRM-GAN) (Rani et al., 2022). Due to the incorporation of
 163 various loss functions and additional computational constraints, the input images are resized to $512 \times 512 \times 3$
 164 and normalized to the range of $[-1, 1]$.

Figure 5. Bone Suppression GAN Architecture: The generator processes the input X-ray through convolutional and pooling layers to extract features, compresses them in a bottleneck layer, and reconstructs a bone-suppressed image via upsampling. The discriminator classifies the generated and real images, distinguishing between real and synthetic outputs.

165 Discriminator

166 The architecture of the discriminator, illustrated in Figure 6, progressively downsamples the input
 167 to determine whether an image is real or generated (real vs. fake); in our case, whether the image is
 168 suppressed or synthesized. To enhance training stability and accelerate convergence, batch normalization is
 169 applied after every convolutional layer except the first one. Each convolutional layer employs a stride of 2,
 170 effectively halving the spatial dimensions of the feature maps at each stage. This systematic reduction in size
 171 enables efficient downsampling of the input image while preserving essential features for discrimination.

Figure 6. Discriminator architecture with down-sampling Conv2D layers, batch normalization, and a linear activation function. Filters and strides are noted for each layer. The f = a number of filters and A = activation function, which is, in this case, linear.

172 Generator

173 The generator architecture in Figure 7 is modeled primarily after the U-net framework, which has
 174 demonstrated strong performance in bone suppression tasks, as evidenced by the results presented in
 175 Section 3.2. The architecture employs a series of convolutional blocks to progressively extract and encode
 176 complex features at multiple hierarchical levels, culminating in the bottleneck layer. Following this,
 177 transpose convolutions are applied to incrementally double the spatial dimensions of the feature maps.

Figure 7. Generator architecture with downsampling path (left) and an upsampling path (right) with skip connections between corresponding layers. Convolutional blocks progressively extract features, culminating in a bottleneck layer. Transpose convolutions in the upsampling path restore spatial resolution, while skip connections preserve fine details, enabling precise feature localization.

178 To maintain spatial consistency and preserve critical features that may be lost during downsampling, the
 179 upsampled outputs are concatenated with corresponding feature maps from the encoder path through skip
 180 connections.

181 During the GAN training process, the generator and discriminator networks are trained simultaneously.
 182 Automatic differentiation, implemented using gradient tape, plays a key role in updating the network
 183 weights efficiently. The generator produces sample images, while the discriminator evaluates them,
 184 distinguishing between real and generated images. Both networks continuously adjust their weights based
 185 on the computed gradients, improving their performance through an iterative feedback loop. This ongoing
 186 refinement continues until the generator successfully produces images with effectively suppressed bone
 187 structures.

188 2.4 Loss Functions and Evaluation Metrics

189 We need some metrics to assess how well a model has performed; in our case, we have selected two
 190 evaluation metrics: the Structural Similarity Index Measure and the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio. Loss
 191 functions are either a combination of the evaluation metrics used as losses or completely different functions.
 192 These metrics provide quantitative ways to assess the effectiveness of bone suppression algorithms and
 193 are also used in other publications (Lam et al., 2022), (Kalisz and Marczyk, 2021), (Gusarev et al., 2017),
 194 (Ren et al., 2021b), (Rani et al., 2022).

195 2.4.1 Evaluation metrics

196 It is essential to define suitable evaluation metrics to measure and compare the performance of the models.
 197 In this study, we will employ the same metrics used in previous research, namely the Multi-Scale Structural
 198 Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM) and the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR).

199 Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM)

200 The generated images are compared with the target images in terms of their structural similarity. A high
 201 MS-SSIM value indicates a more remarkable similarity in the structure of the target and the generated
 202 images (Hore and Ziou, 2010). MS-SSIM is a crucial metric for assessing image quality, extending
 203 beyond the traditional Structural Similarity Index Measure by incorporating multiple scales and structural
 204 features. It evaluates how well structural information is preserved between a reference image and a distorted
 205 version, offering a more comprehensive assessment of perceptual image quality. The Structural Similarity
 206 Index Measure equation consists of three components: i) luminance comparison function, defined as
 207 $l(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y+c_1)}{(\mu_x^2+\mu_y^2+c_1)}$, ii) contrast comparison function, defined as $c(x, y) = \frac{2\sigma_x\sigma_y+c_2}{\sigma_x^2+\sigma_y^2+c_2}$, and iii) structure
 208 comparison function, defined as $s(x, y) = \frac{\sigma_{xy}+c_3}{\sigma_x\sigma_y+c_3}$, where x is the reference image (ground truth), y is the
 209 distorted image (predicted), μ_x, μ_y are the pixel sample means of x and y , σ_x^2, σ_y^2 are the variances of x
 210 and y , and σ_{xy} is the covariance of x and y ; c_1, c_2, c_3 are the variables to stabilize the division with a weak
 211 denominator. The SSIM is given as a weighted combination of these comparative measures, formulated as:

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = l(x, y)^\alpha \cdot c(x, y)^\beta \cdot s(x, y)^\gamma \quad (1)$$

212 where α, β , and γ are the weights of the appropriate comparison functions. By setting these weights to 1,
 213 the formula simplifies to:

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (2)$$

214 .
215 After adding multiple scales and structural characteristics, the MS-SSIM is expressed as follows:

$$\text{MS-SSIM}(x, y) = [l_M(x, y)]^\alpha \cdot \prod_{j=1}^M [c_j(x, y)]^\beta \cdot [s_j(x, y)]^\gamma \quad (3)$$

216 where $l_M(x, y)$ is the luminance comparison function on the M-th scale (coarsest), $c_j(x, y)$ is the contrast
217 comparison function on the j-th scale, $s_j(x, y)$ is the structure comparison function on the j-th scale and M
218 is the number of scales used for the calculation of MS-SSIM.

219 Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)

220 The PSNR quantifies the relationship between the highest possible signal strength, represented by the
221 original image, and the noise level, which arises from differences between the original and processed
222 images. This value is measured in decibels (dB). A higher PSNR indicates greater similarity between
223 the original and processed images, signifying better image quality. In contrast, a lower PSNR suggests
224 increased distortion or noise in the reconstructed image (Hore and Ziou, 2010).

225 The PSNR is expressed as follows:

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \times \log_{10} \frac{\text{MAX}^2}{\text{MSE}} \quad (4)$$

226 where MAX is the maximum possible pixel value of the image and MSE is a result of the Mean Squared
227 Error (MSE), a common metric for measuring the difference between actual and predicted values, which is
228 calculated as $\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - p_i)^2$, where n is the number of observations in the dataset, y_i is the
229 ground truth value, and p_i is the predicted value.

230 2.4.2 Loss functions

231 The Mean Squared Error (MSE), the Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index Measure (MS-SSIM), and a
232 combination of either MSE or MAE with MS-SSIM are utilized as loss functions. The MS-SSIM is already
233 defined in the metrics section, see Section 2.4. The loss function based on the MS-SSIM metric will be
234 denoted as L_{MSSIM} in the following text.

235 The MSE, also referred to as L_2 , is a fundamental metric that quantifies the mean squared differences
236 between the observed and predicted values. As mentioned earlier, it plays a crucial role in evaluating
237 prediction quality by emphasizing larger errors. In contrast, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), known as
238 L_1 , calculates the mean absolute deviations between the predictions and the true values, disregarding the
239 direction of the errors. It is computed as

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - p_i| \quad (5)$$

240 where n represents the number of observations in the dataset, y_i is the ground truth value, and p_i is the
 241 predicted value. Unlike L_2 , L_1 is less sensitive to outliers, as it does not disproportionately penalize large
 242 deviations. The combination of L_2 or L_1 with L_{MSSSIM} , referred to as Mixed Loss, was first introduced by
 243 M. Gusarev (Gusarev et al., 2017). Although L_2 performs well, tests indicate that noise in critical regions
 244 affects the results. This is where L_{MSSSIM} proves advantageous, as it preserves contrast in high-frequency
 245 regions. L_1 Mixed Loss (L_{MixL_1}) and (L_{MixL_2}) Mixed Loss are defined as follows:

$$L_{MixL_1} = \alpha \cdot L_{MSSSIM} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot L_1 \quad (6)$$

$$L_{MixL_2} = \alpha \cdot L_{MSSSIM} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot L_2 \quad (7)$$

246 where α is a hyperparameter.

247 The L_2 function is convex and differentiable, making it more suitable for optimization. However, since it
 248 is insensitive to small changes, it is complemented by the MS-SSIM loss, which primarily focuses on local
 249 neighborhood variations. In some experiments, L_1 is used instead of L_2 to assess whether L_2 yields better
 250 results than L_1 . As noted in (Rani et al., 2022), L_1 loss is an effective method for capturing low-frequency
 251 details such as color, contrast, and luminance, producing sharper images compared to L_2 loss, making it
 252 the preferred base function. Since no results confirm this in the case of bone suppression, the tests will be
 253 performed here.

254 Loss Functions for the generator and the discriminator

255 The concept of Wasserstein Loss (Arjovsky et al., 2017) is derived from the Wasserstein distance, also
 256 known as the Earth-Mover's distance. It is calculated by taking the average of the critic's outputs for
 257 real data and subtracting the average of its outputs for generated data. The critic aims to maximize this
 258 difference by assigning higher scores to real data and lower scores to generated data, whereas the generator
 259 strives to minimize this difference by producing data that the critic perceives as real. The equation used to
 260 compute the Wasserstein Loss is as follows:

$$L_{cGAN}(G, D) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [D(X_i, Y'_i) - D(X_i, Y_i)] \quad (8)$$

261 where $L_{cGAN}(G, D)$ is the loss of the critic, G is the generator, and D is the critic; $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n$ is an average
 262 for all n samples in the batch; $D(X_i, Y'_i)$ is the output of the critic for the real data pair, and $D(X_i, Y_i)$ is
 263 the output of the critic for the generated data pair.

264 This loss function is consistently applied to the discriminator across all experiments and is also
 265 incorporated into the generator's loss formulation. Four distinct loss functions derived from the Wasserstein
 266 distance are evaluated. As the complexity of the loss function increases, a larger volume of training data is
 267 required, as discussed in Section 3.3.

268 For the generator, the following loss functions are used and tested:

269 Wasserstein + L1/L2 loss

$$L_{\text{cGAN}}(G) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y'_i) + \delta [\alpha L_{L1/L2}] \quad (9)$$

270 Wasserstein + L1/L2 loss + Perceptual Loss

$$L_{\text{cGAN}}(G) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y'_i) + \delta [\alpha L_{L1/L2} + \beta L_{\text{Perceptual}}] \quad (10)$$

271 Wasserstein + L1/L2 loss + Perceptual Loss + Sobel Loss

$$L_{\text{cGAN}}(G) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y'_i) + \delta [\alpha L_{L1/L2} + \beta L_{\text{Perceptual}} + \gamma L_{\text{Sobel}}] \quad (11)$$

272 where $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n D(X_i, Y'_i)$ is the average score that the discriminator gives to the generated data across n
 273 samples, X_i is the conditioning input, and Y'_i is the generator-generated output; $\delta, \alpha, \beta, \gamma$ are the weight
 274 parameters for the additional loss components; $\alpha L_{L1/L2}$ is the result of the L_1 or L_2 multiplied by the
 275 weight parameter α . $L_{\text{Perceptual}}$ is the loss function, also known as VGG-19 Loss, which employs the
 276 VGG-19 model pre-trained on ImageNet. This function enhances image synthesis quality by ensuring
 277 that the generated feature maps closely resemble those of the target image. It achieves this by measuring
 278 the Euclidean distance between the feature representations of the generated and target images, thereby
 279 improving information retention and reducing artifacts. The model can also be used with other deep learning
 280 architectures, such as ResNet50 and ResNet101, provided they are trained within the appropriate image
 281 domain (Johnson et al., 2016). The result of $L_{\text{Perceptual}}$ is multiplied by the weight parameter β . L_{Sobel} is a
 282 loss function inspired by edge detection techniques. It calculates errors by comparing gradient maps of
 283 the generated and target images in both the X and Y directions, effectively capturing discrepancies in
 284 image gradients (Lu and Chen, 2022). The result of L_{Sobel} is multiplied by the weight parameter γ . For all
 285 experiments, including all combinations of loss functions, the hyperparameters are defined as $\delta = 10000$,
 286 $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 10$, and $\gamma = 10$. The primary objective of the loss function, which integrates Wasserstein Loss,
 287 L_1/L_2 loss, Perceptual Loss, and Sobel Loss, is to capture both low- and high-frequency details within the
 288 image. This approach is intended to enhance detail preservation, ensuring that essential structures remain
 289 intact even after bone suppression.

3 RESULTS

290 Determining the optimal parameter settings for different approaches and datasets requires both theoretical
 291 knowledge and sufficient time. To identify the most suitable parameters, we conducted a series of
 292 experiments, systematically adjusting not only the parameters but also the network architecture, including
 293 all layers and loss functions.

294 The implementation was carried out using Python 3.6.8, TensorFlow 2.6.2, Segmentation Models v.1.0.1,
 295 and CUDA 11.4. The hardware setup included 20× Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6154 CPUs (@ 3.00 GHz), 2×
 296 NVIDIA TESLA V100 GPUs (32 GB), and 7.3 TB of RAM. The system operated on RedHat 6.0.11.

297 The reported training times for individual experiments serve only as approximations, providing insight
 298 into the computational demands of various approaches and how these demands vary depending on dataset
 299 size and complexity.

300 3.1 Results for Autoencoders

301 Since there are many experiments, showing only the best result according to the dataset size should help
 302 with readability. Training of all models uses the Adam optimizer (Kingma and Ba, 2017), configured with
 303 a fixed learning rate of 0.001. Furthermore, a decay factor of 0.5 is employed with a patience parameter set
 304 to 5 in relation to the validation loss.

Table 1. Best results for autoencoder experiments

Train/Test size	Loss function	Training time (s)	MSE	MS-SSIM	PSNR
400/100	$L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$	1 612	0.000877	0.9805	31.332
1000/100	L_{MSSSIM}	3 853	0.000819	0.9827	31.935
3980/100	$L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$	27 606	0.000641	0.9847	32.850

305 As shown in Table 1, the best-performing model was trained on 3,980 samples using the Mixed Loss
 306 with the L_1 loss function ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$), with a training duration of approximately 7.7 hours. The other models,
 307 which utilized the Mixed Loss with the L_2 loss function and the MS-SSIM loss function, demonstrated
 308 slightly lower performance, suggesting that the number of training samples has only a minor impact on
 309 overall effectiveness.

310 To further enhance performance, the feature extractor from a more complex pre-trained model was
 311 integrated, replacing the encoder. Specifically, ResNet50 and FPN + EfficientNetB0 were used as backbone
 312 architectures. All experiments in this setup were trained with the Mixed Loss using L_2 ($L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$) on a
 313 dataset comprising 3,980 training samples and 100 test samples, as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Results for autoencoder experiments with pre-trained encoder

Backbone	Training time (s)	MSE	MS-SSIM	PSNR
ResNet50	20 989	0.000692	0.9856	31.981
FPN + EfficientNetB0	38 989	0.000484	0.9909	33.541

314 The findings of this experiment indicate that the use of a pre-trained encoder does not inherently lead to a
 315 notable performance gain. While the Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) with EfficientNetB0 achieves better
 316 performance compared to the previous autoencoder (AE) models, the improvement remains relatively
 317 modest.

318 3.2 Results for U-net and models from Segmentation Models library

319 For the U-Net experiments, the dataset size is limited to a maximum of 3,980 training samples and 100
 320 test samples. This study evaluates the classic U-Net, as well as U-Net and FPN with various backbones
 321 from the Segmentation Models library. The experimental setup uses a batch size of 4 and epochs set to 50.
 322 All models are trained using the Adam optimizer (Kingma and Ba, 2017) with a learning rate of 0.001.
 323 Additionally, a decay factor of 0.5 is applied with patience set to 5, based on validation loss.

Table 3. Results for the experiments of U-net written from scratch

Loss function	Training time(s)	MSE	MS-SSIM	PSNR
L_2	53 992	0.000900	0.9756	31.396
L_{MSSSIM}	56 248	0.000627	0.9908	33.389
L_{MixL_2}	56 402	0.000530	0.9915	33.877

324 Table 3 indicates that the Mixed Loss with L_2 is the most effective choice for this architecture. The U-Net
 325 demonstrates a significant improvement over the autoencoder (AE), surpassing its best-performing models,
 326 with a training duration of just over 15.6 hours.

Table 4. Results for the experiments using Segmentation models library

Architecture	Loss function	Training time(s)	MSE	MS-SSIM	PSNR
U-net(EfficientNetB0)	L_{MixL_2}	14 217	0.000172	0.9962	38.590
U-net(EfficientNetB0)	L_{MixL_1}	37 093	0.000177	0.9955	38.536
FPN(ResNet50)	L_{MixL_2}	45 671	0.000360	0.9941	35.365
FPN(EfficientNetB0)	L_{MixL_2}	61 050	0.000192	0.9950	37.956

327 The more advanced models from the Segmentation Models library significantly outperformed the previous
 328 models, as shown in Table 4. The best-performing model utilized EfficientNetB0 as its backbone, which
 329 also yielded the highest accuracy in evaluations beyond this study. Another advantage of this library is the
 330 reduced training time—training the best model required only approximately 4 hours. Among the tested
 331 loss functions, the Mixed Loss with L_2 (L_{MixL_2}) achieved the best results; however, further experiments
 332 are necessary to determine the most effective loss function.

333 3.3 Results for Generative Adversarial Networks

334 A series of experiments were conducted to determine the optimal layer configuration and hyperparameters
 335 for the GAN model. This section presents only the best-performing models based on the dataset size.

336 All experiments performed here use an input image with a resolution of $512 \times 512 \times 3$, with a batch size
 337 of 4 for experiments using 3000 training samples and a batch size of 8 for others. The loss functions are:
 338 $WL_2 = \text{Wasserstein Loss} + L_2$, $WL_1PS = \text{Wasserstein Loss} + L_1 + \text{Perceptual Loss} + \text{Sobel Loss}$.

Table 5. Best results for the GAN experiments

Train/Test size	Loss function	Training time (s)	Epochs	MS-SSIM	PSNR
400/100	WL_2	41 232	500	0.9876	35.619
1900/100	WL_1PS	290 017	750	0.9938	40.535
3000/100	WL_1PS	468 202	750	0.9968	44.085

339 Table 5 indicates that the GAN trained on 3,000 samples using the Wasserstein + L_1 + Perceptual + Sobel
 340 Loss achieved the best performance. However, a notable drawback is the training time, which extended to
 341 5.4 days. The number of training samples significantly influences the model's performance. The findings of
 342 my experiments align with the proposition in the SFRM-GAN paper (Rani et al., 2022), which suggested
 343 that L_1 loss should outperform L_2 when combined with Wasserstein, Perceptual, and Sobel Losses.

3.4 Comparative analysis between the models

Since the Autoencoder and U-Net models are trained at a resolution of $1024 \times 1024 \times 1$, while the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) models operate at $512 \times 512 \times 3$, a direct comparison between these architectures may not provide meaningful insights. To address this, additional experiments were conducted in this section, where the best-performing AE and U-Net models were modified and retrained to match the $512 \times 512 \times 3$ resolution.

Training the GAN model at a higher resolution of $1024 \times 1024 \times 3$, which requires three channels, presents significant computational and time constraints. This section presents the results of these experiments and outlines the specific computational requirements for training the GAN model at this increased resolution.

A comparison of our findings with results from other studies in the field is provided at the end of this chapter. First, a direct comparison between the two models will be presented, followed by an experiment demonstrating how each model reconstructs an image from the test set, allowing for the calculation of MS-SSIM and PSNR metrics.

Table 6. Direct comparison of the best models

Model	Training time	MS-SSIM	PSNR
FPN + EfficientNetB0 ($L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	38 989	0.9909	33.541
U-net (Segmentation Models + $L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	14 217	0.9962	38.590
GAN (WL₁PS)	468 202	0.9968	44.085

Table 6 indicates that the GAN model delivers the best performance, with the only notable drawback being the extended training time of approximately 5.4 days. An interesting observation is that the MS-SSIM values remain relatively high across all approaches, suggesting that image reconstruction is effectively performed. However, PSNR plays a crucial role in determining the overall visual quality of the reconstructed images.

To further examine the influence of PSNR on reconstruction quality, we present a series of comparative figures in Figure 8. These visualizations will display each reconstructed image alongside its corresponding test sample, both with and without bone suppression, providing clearer insight into the impact of PSNR on the final output.

Table 7. Direct comparison of the best models on test image

Model	MS-SSIM	PSNR
c) FPN + EfficientNetB0 ($L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	0.9821	36.07
d) U-net (Segmentation Models + $L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	0.9963	38.52
e) GAN (WL₁PS)	0.9985	45.61

Table 7 presents the MS-SSIM and PSNR values for each model in comparison to the original image. The results indicate that the GAN model achieves the best performance, with the highest PSNR. It is important to note the difference in input dimensions among the models: the GAN processes images at $512 \times 512 \times 3$, while both the Autoencoder and U-Net operate with a larger format of $1024 \times 1024 \times 1$. The visual outcomes of this experiment are illustrated in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8. Best results for direct comparison, where: (c) FPN + EfficientNetB0, MSSSIM: 0.9821 and PSNR: 36.07; (d) U-net from Segmentation models, MSSSIM: 0.9963 and PSNR: 38.52; (e) GAN, MSSSIM: 0.9985 and PSNR 45.61 (Output images resized to 512×512).

371 **3.5 Comparative Analysis for 512×512 Input Size**

372 To enable a direct comparison, the performance of models trained at the same resolution of 512×512
 373 will be evaluated. Following this, an experiment will be conducted to analyze the reconstructed images,
 374 highlighting differences in MS-SSIM and PSNR on a test sample.

375 The training parameters for the autoencoder and U-Net models were set to a batch size of 4 and 50 epochs.

Table 8. Direct comparison of the best models trained on 512×512 input size

Model	Training time	MS-SSIM	PSNR
AE (L_{MixL_1})	4 803	0.9837	31.70
FPN + EfficientNetB0 (L_{MixL_2})	-	-	-
U-net (L_{MixL_2})	14 067	0.9915	33.88
U-net (Segmentation Models + L_{MixL_2})	9 706	0.9955	37.59
GAN (WL_1PS)	468 202	0.9968	44.09

376 Table 8 shows that there is no significant difference in performance between models trained at 1024×1024
 377 and those trained at 512×512 . Once again, the GAN model achieved the best results, with consistently
 378 high MS-SSIM values across all cases. The most notable differences appear in PSNR, which can be visually
 379 examined alongside the original and target images. Additionally, the FPN model failed to train due to an
 380 unresolved issue.

Table 9. Direct comparison of the best models trained on 512×512 on test image

Model	MS-SSIM	PSNR
c) AE ($L_{\text{Mix}L_1}$)	0.9804	33.60
d) U-net ($L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	0.9919	37.25
e) U-net (Segmentation Models + $L_{\text{Mix}L_2}$)	0.9957	40.01
f) GAN (WL₁PS)	0.9985	45.61

381 The results for the 512×512 models are presented in Table 9. The GAN model achieved the highest
 382 PSNR by a significant margin, demonstrating superior performance.

4 DISCUSSION

383 In this study, three methodologies previously applied to this task were implemented and rigorously
 384 evaluated: autoencoders (AE), U-Net, and generative adversarial networks (GAN). Each of these methods
 385 operates on a distinct principle, making this study not only an assessment of their effectiveness but also
 386 a comparison to determine the most suitable approach for this task. Autoencoders and U-Net, as non-
 387 generative models, tend to be less susceptible to spurious noise introduced during training or inference.
 388 However, the quality of the reconstructed images may sometimes be suboptimal, potentially complicating
 389 the diagnosis based on the X-ray output. In contrast, generative adversarial networks, due to their inherently
 390 generative nature, can exhibit greater sensitivity to such noise; yet, they outperformed the other approaches
 391 overall based on quantitative metrics. Each architecture was systematically designed and evaluated across
 392 a range of parameters, with the optimal configurations selected for the final assessment. It is essential
 393 to emphasize that medical X-ray images require interpretation by a qualified healthcare professional for
 394 accurate clinical diagnosis.

395 One of the first methods to address the bone (rib) suppression challenge was the multiresolution
 396 massive training artificial neural network (MTANN) (Suzuki et al., 2006), which employed
 397 decomposition/composition techniques and was trained on chest radiographs and dual energy bone images.
 398 This method produced "bone-image-like" outputs, enabling the creation of "soft-tissue-image-like" images
 399 with effectively suppressed ribs and clavicles. Despite such advancements, bone removal in radiological
 400 imaging remains a significant challenge, as evidenced by numerous recent studies focusing on refining
 401 existing methods, comparing them, optimizing workflows, and addressing limitations to improve usability
 402 for radiologists and physicians. A major challenge in the bone suppression task is the scarcity of bone
 403 suppressed data and the general lack of publicly available datasets, as reported (Ren et al., 2021a; Schiller
 404 et al., 2025). The state-of-the-art methods include deep learning architectures based mainly on autoencoders
 405 (AE), U-net, and, more recently, generative adversarial networks.

406 Convolutional denoising autoencoders were chosen for this task, as the ribs in X-ray images are considered
 407 to be a form of noise. This unsupervised machine learning technique was used because it learns to map
 408 corrupted data (bones) to uncorrupted data (bone-suppressed images) by minimizing a loss function. This

409 approach has previously been used by Gusarev et al. (Gusarev et al., 2017) and Kalisz et al. (Kalisz and
410 Marczyk, 2021). Our results indicate that the best performance is achieved by the autoencoder with a
411 pre-trained encoder (FPN + EfficientNetB0) (Table 2). However, the performance improvement is not as
412 significant as with the autoencoder implemented from scratch (Table 1). In direct comparison to other
413 methods, the autoencoder achieved the worst results (Table 9). Compared to the implementation by Gusarev
414 et al. (Gusarev et al., 2017), our AE-based approach with a pre-trained encoder achieved a better MS-SSIM
415 value (Table 10).

416 The U-Net (Ronneberger et al., 2015) is a widely used neural network in medical imaging, mainly
417 designed for image segmentation (Siddique et al., 2021). Due to its adaptability, various modifications and
418 integrations have been applied to bone suppression workflows in X-ray images (Li et al., 2020; Xu et al.,
419 2024; Schiller et al., 2025), making it a relevant choice for this study.

420 Schiller et al. (Schiller et al., 2025) developed xU-NetFullSharp, an advanced deep learning model for
421 bone suppression based on the U-NetSharp architecture, originally designed for medical image segmentation
422 (Zunair and Hamza, 2021). The xU-NetFullSharp improves performance by incorporating multi-scale skip
423 connections from shallow layer blocks to deeper layers, enhancing the model's ability to retain low-level
424 contextual information. They also implemented several U-Net-based architectures using TensorFlow and
425 Keras, in combination with NumPy and OpenCV, including U-Net, Attention U-Net, U-Net++, Attention
426 U-Net++, U-Net3+, U-NetSharp, and xU-NetFullSharp. Subsequently, these architectures were compared
427 with the latest models for bone suppression, namely the autoencoder proposed by (Kalisz and Marczyk,
428 2021) and the ensemble model DeBoNet (Rajaraman et al., 2022).

429 Our U-Net-based approach, which integrates Segmentation Models with a Mixed L_2 Loss function,
430 outperformed xU-NetFullSharp in the reported evaluation metrics. Specifically, our model achieved an MS-
431 SSIM of 0.996 and a PSNR of 38.59, while xU-NetFullSharp obtained an MS-SSIM of 0.986 and a PSNR
432 of 33.81 (Table 10). Compared directly to the autoencoder, our U-Net-based architecture demonstrated
433 superior MS-SSIM and PSNR values but was outperformed by the GAN, which achieved the highest results
434 in both metrics (Table 9).

435 Oh and Yun (Oh and Yun, 2018) used a denoising approach based on conditional image-to-image
436 translation with adversarial training within a GAN framework to model the conditional probability
437 distribution of the output (bone-suppressed X-ray images) given the input (original X-ray images). In
438 addition, Liang et al. (Liang et al., 2020) demonstrated that GANs could effectively learn the nuances of
439 bone suppression using adversarial learning techniques, resulting in images that preserve essential soft
440 tissue details while minimizing bone artifacts. To improve image quality, GANs facilitate the generation of
441 bone-suppressed images in a more automated and efficient manner. Techniques such as CycleGAN and
442 conditional GAN have been employed to enhance the bone suppression process, allowing the simultaneous
443 generation of bone-free images and organ segmentation (Zhou et al., 2020; Eslami et al., 2020).

444 In 2020, Zhou et al. (Zhou et al., 2020) incorporated enforced semantic features into a dilated conditional
445 GAN, which allows for a better contextual understanding of the images being processed. This integration
446 not only improves the quality of the generated images but also aligns the output more closely with clinical
447 expectations. Their model was trained by enforcing the pixel-wise intensity similarity and the semantic-
448 level visual similarity between the generated x-ray images and the ground truth by optimizing an L_1
449 loss of the pixel intensity values on the generator side and a feature matching loss on the discriminator
450 side. Since a naïve combination of adversarial loss and pixel-wise L_1 loss failed to capture the semantic
451 information of X-ray images, a feature matching loss was introduced on top of the discriminator. This

Table 10. Comparison of the models with other articles

Name	Model and technique	MS-SSIM	PSNR
[Gusarev et al. 2017]	Autoencoder and convolutional layers	0.907	-
[Eslami et al. 2020]	Conditional GAN and dilated convolutions	0.970	-
[Chen et al. 2019]	Cascade of multiscale CNN	0.977	39.40
[Zhou et al. 2018]	Multi-scale and conditional adversarial network	0.884	39.7
[Huang et al. 2020]	U-Net3+	0.985	33.69
[Kalisz et al. 2021]	Autoencoder and convolutional layers	0.982	32.60
[Rajaraman et al. 2021b]	Residual Network Model (ResNet-BS)	0.949	34.07
[Ziviani et al. 2022]	Conditional GAN	0.943	34.97
[Rani et al. 2022]	SFRM - GAN	0.989	42.83
[Zunair and Hamza, 2021]	U-NetSharp	0.985	33.72
[Schiller et al. 2024]	xU-NetFullSharp	0.986	33.81
<i>Our approach</i>	<i>FPN + EfficientNetB0 (L_{MixL_2})</i>	<i>0.991</i>	<i>33.54</i>
<i>Our approach</i>	<i>U-net (Segmentation Models + L_{MixL_2})</i>	<i>0.996</i>	<i>38.59</i>
Our approach	GAN (WL1PS)	0.997	44.09

452 approach allowed the discriminator to extract feature representations from each pair of real and generated
 453 images using activations from its fourth convolutional block and to compute the mean of the element-wise
 454 L_1 distance between them. the resulting loss function for optimizing the discriminator was defined as
 455 $D^* = \mathcal{L}_{adv_D} + \lambda_{fm}\mathcal{L}_{fm}$, where L_{adv_D} is the adversarial loss of the discriminator, L_{fm} is the feature
 456 matching loss, and λ_{fm} is a constant to adjust the weight of the feature matching loss. The utilization of
 457 feature matching loss enforced the similarity of high-level feature maps.

458 Our GAN architecture, enhanced by the incorporation of Wasserstein Loss along with L_1 loss, Perceptual
 459 Loss, and Sobel Loss functions, delivered the best performance. Its metrics, including a PSNR of 44.09
 460 dB and an MS-SSIM of 0.9968, confirm the model's ability to suppress bone structures effectively while
 461 preserving high image quality and critical soft tissue details. Compared to other studies (Ziviani et al., 2022;
 462 Rani et al., 2022; Eslami et al., 2020), which used the same dataset for evaluation, our method performed
 463 the best, achieving an MS-SSIM value of 0.997 and a PSNR of 44.09.

464 Comparison with other articles is presented in Table 10. These results are intended primarily to provide an
 465 illustrative benchmark. However, it is important to emphasize that there remains room for further research.
 466 This observation is critical because it underscores that, despite the progress detailed in this work, the field
 467 still offers significant opportunities for further exploration.

5 CONCLUSION

468 The increased visibility of the lung regions in bone-suppressed images can significantly aid in detecting
 469 small lesions and nodules, thus improving diagnostic accuracy. This makes the proposed GAN architecture
 470 a promising tool for medical imaging preprocessing tasks. Notably, the GAN architecture presented in this
 471 study is innovative, particularly due to the use of a custom loss function that combines four well-established
 472 components: L_1 , Wasserstein Loss, Perceptual Loss, and Sobel loss. This combination enables the model to
 473 effectively balance pixel-level accuracy, perceptual similarity, edge preservation, and global image realism,
 474 which are all crucial for maintaining diagnostically relevant features in the generated outputs.

475 In addition to the GAN-based approach, we also trained models for bone removal using autoencoders
 476 and a custom implementation of the U-Net architecture from scratch. However, their performance across

477 the evaluated metrics was consistently lower compared to the proposed GAN model, highlighting the
478 advantage of integrating multiple loss components in this context.

479 The source code and trained models developed in this work are publicly available to the research
480 community on GitHub, promoting transparency, reproducibility, and further development in this important
481 area.

482 Future studies could explore its integration into clinical workflows, where collaboration with radiologists
483 can provide critical insights into its practical impact on diagnosis. In addition, future advances, including
484 optimized training strategies, refined loss functions, and adaptation to other imaging modalities that demand
485 high detail denoising and feature preservation, could further enhance the utility of this approach. The
486 findings of this research lay the foundation for improved computer-aided diagnosis and more robust image
487 processing solutions in the medical domain.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

488 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
489 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

490 **Lukáš Jochymek:** Methodology, Software, Writing - Original draft, Data Curation, Visualization. **Markéta**
491 **Vašinková:** Writing - original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Vít Doleží:** Conceptualization,
492 Methodology, Writing - Original draft. **Petr Gajdoš:** Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration,
493 Funding acquisition, Supervision.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

496 The datasets analyzed in this study are publicly available through the Japanese Society of Radiological
497 Technology (JSRT) at: <http://db.jsrt.or.jp/eng.php>.

CODE AVAILABILITY

498 The source code used in this study is publicly available at: [https://github.com/lowoncuties/](https://github.com/lowoncuties/Bone-suppression-in-X-Ray-medical-images-of-lungs)
499 `Bone-suppression-in-X-Ray-medical-images-of-lungs`.

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